

PERFORMANCE OF LIGHTWEIGHT HYBRID COMPOSITES BASED ON PA6 FOR LOAD-BEARING AUTOMOTIVE PARTS: INFLUENCE OF PROCESS AND USE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Thanks to their excellent properties fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are attracting considerable attention from several industries, such as the automotive industry. Their main advantages are lightness (compared to metals) which reduces energy consumption and therefore engine emissions, toughness and recyclability (compared to thermosets). Thermoforming process of thermoplastic laminates reinforced with continuous fibers associated with injection molding of discontinuous reinforced thermoplastic in order to add stiffeners or specific functions at precisely defined locations is increasingly used for applications which require structural lightweight parts.

In this study which is made in the framework of FUI project ARIZONA, complex shaped components were fabricated from thermoplastic prepreg combined with injected composite. Tepex®, the commercial name of the thermoplastic prepreg is a balanced fabric with 0° and 90° oriented E-glass fibers and polyamide 6 (PA6). The injected composite is made with the same grade of polyamide and reinforced with short E-glass fibers. All materials were supplied by Bond-Laminates GmbH. The prepreg lay-up was consolidated as a plate, pre-heated with an IR heating system, and put inside the mold. The plate was then thermoformed by closing the mold and over-molded in one step.

The aim of this work was to characterize the mechanical performance of the laminate zones, and the adhesion bonding between the formed laminates and the over-molded discontinuous fiber reinforced composite in relation with the processing parameters for different environments use (moisture). Specimens were obtained from parts using water jet cutting and mechanical tests were performed using a universal testing machine equipped with Acoustic Emission recorder. Full field strain data were obtained with Stereo Digital Image Correlation (DIC). Two CCD cameras simultaneously take pictures of the speckled surface of the specimen. The pairs of images are then correlated by a computer algorithm that calculates a representation of the surface as well as the in-plane and out-of-plan displacements and strains. The morphology of the fiber network and the interface between the over-molded reinforced thermoplastic and the formed composite laminate were analyzed on the specimen after water cutting and polishing, using digital or electronic microscopy and X-ray micro-computed tomography for 3D investigations.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the automotive industry has experienced considerable technological development, according to a demand for more and more challenging. Today, due to the globalization car manufacturers are innovating every day, in a sense of growing competition in the market by introducing vehicles more comfortable, safe, economic and environmentally friendly throughout.

In this way the choice of materials became an important step in the eco-conception, which can contribute significantly in environment preservation. Composite materials with organic matrix can be good alternative to replacement of classical metallic materials. During the last century, the introduction of advanced composite materials in various industries (aerospace, automotive ...) was a striking success. The strengths of these materials reside in: their lightness, their chemical stability and their implementation facilities. The weight saving has a direct impact on the surrounding, by the considerable decrease of emission of non-desirable gases such as (CO₂).

However, the physical properties of these materials vary depending on several factors in particular the nature of the matrix and the reinforcement, the architecture and the reinforcement rate. In an economic context the use of mid-range materials is preferred in automotive mass production. In this context, the thermoplastic matrix based composites reinforced with glass fiber are good candidates. Recyclability of thermoplastics is one of their various advantages.

One of these materials that are used increasingly in automotive field is polyamide-6 (PA-6), which is a semi crystalline polymer characterized by acceptable mechanical properties, good resistance to fatigue, chemicals and hydrocarbons. But, it has poor resistance to water and its implementation requires drying [1]. The use of this material as matrix constitutes a good candidate for the manufacture of thermoplastic composites reinforced with glass fibers for the automotive industry.

However, at thickness and shape equivalent composite materials based on PA-6 reinforced with glass fibers are not equivalent to steels in terms of overall rigidity.

In order to overcome this difficulty, a new technique of composite manufacture has been developed; this technique is composite over-molding.

This study is made in the framework of FUI project ARIZONA, which consists in a new methodology of composite manufacturing from thermoplastic prepreg combined with injected composite based on PA6 matrix [2, 3].

The objective of this work is to characterize thermo-mechanical and mechanical properties of different zones of the composite part: laminate, injected and over-molded zones in relation with the processing parameters and moisture content.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this study were three Polyamide PA6 based composites. Continuous glass fibers reinforced PA6, commercially named Tepex Dynalyte 102 RG 600(2); the reinforcement of this material is a balanced fabric with 0° and 90° oriented made from two plies of 0.5 mm given a total thickness of 1mm. The reference name of this material is CGFR-PA6. Fiber weight fraction is about 0.64 (cf. Fig.1.1). Injected composite reinforced by discontinuous glass fibers with a nominal length of $250\mu\text{m}$; this material is made with the same grade of PA6 and commercially named Durethan BKV 60 characterized by fiber weight fraction of 0.62 (cf. Fig.1.2). The reference name of this composite is DGFR-PA6. All materials were supplied by Bond-Laminates GmbH[®] and Lanxess[®].

In the aim to characterize the effect of process manufacturing parameters, a prototype part with a complex shape was designed in ARIZONA project. The design was carried out by Mecaplast[®] after shape optimization given by LTDS. The mold was realized by Compose[®]. All prototype parts were manufactured at the PEP. The prepreg lay-up was consolidated as a plate, pre-heated with an IR heating system, and put inside the mold. The plate was then thermoformed by closing the mold and over-molded by injecting the DGFR-PA6 (Fig.1) in one step. Temperature of pre-heating was varied as follow: 250, 270, 285 and 295°C. Mold temperature was 110°C. All specimens were obtained by water jet cutting from prototypes.

Figure 1: Numerical optical micrograph showing over-molded composite layers.

2.2 Thermomechanical analysis

Rheological characteristics of materials were performed with the use of DMA50 0.1dB from METRAVIB on rectangular (20mm×2mm× thickness mm) specimens in the tension/compression mode at controlled alternating strain. The temperature range was -130°C to 200°C with a heating rate of 1°C/min and the frequency was varied from 0.1 to 30 Hz.

2.3 Three-point bending test

The three-point bending loadings were carried out using an INSTRON 4206 electromechanical machine with load cells of 5 kN and the cross-head speed was 2.5 mm/min. The radius of the load roller was 5 mm and the support span was 60 mm. Experimental procedure was made according to the International standard ISO 14125 at room temperature ($T=23\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 40\pm 5\%$). CGFR-PA6 samples have the following dimensions: 100 mm long, 25 mm wide and 1 mm thick. In the case of DGFR-PA6 and over-molded composite the samples dimensions are $100 \times 15 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ and $100 \times 15 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ respectively.

2.4 Tensile test

The monotonic tensile strength was measured using a MTS Bionix (Model 370.02) axial/torsion tester equipped with a 25 kN load cell and a displacement sensor at room temperature ($T=23\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 40\pm 5\%$) at a cross-head speed of 2.5 mm/min.

Tensile test was carried out only for the composite reinforced with continuous glass fiber (CGFR-PA6); fibers were oriented at $0/90^\circ$ according to the loading direction. Specimen dimension was 250 mm long, 25 mm wide and 1 mm thick. Aluminum tabs ($50 \times 25 \text{ mm}^2$) were bonded on the ends of the tested specimens in order to minimize the stress concentration due to the tightening of grips.

Stereo-correlation technique was used to calculate in and out of plane strain field. This technique provides displacements in all direction of loaded specimens. Two cameras record simultaneously the same object in a different angle (cf. fig.2). The correlation algorithm compares gray level of each pixel in subset defined in the region of interest (ROI). Once the matching is done, the displacement components of the center of the reference and deformed subset can be determined. The strain field is then derived from the filtered displacement field [4]. However, the accuracy of correlation is highly linked to the presence of random texture in the surface. Generally in composite materials testing, surfaces should be prepared before mechanical tests by creating speckles white on a black background.

Figure 2: Digital stereo-correlation device.

In order to correlate the stereo-images, the correlation algorithm needs information on the orientation and position parameters of the cameras as well as the intrinsic parameters of each camera. These parameters are determined by calibrating the stereo-vision set up which is done by recording images of a calibration target. The system used in our laboratory is Vic3D developed by Correlated Solutions[®].

2.5 Acoustic Emission (AE) device

Acoustic Emissions (AE) are the local dissipation of energy stored in form of elastic energy. Sources of acoustic emission can be associated to different phenomena like crack initiation and crack

growth opening and closure. Therefore, AE is the mechanical or ultrasonic manifestation of micro-displacements in the internal structure of the material.

When the material is mechanically loaded, waves with various nature and frequency are propagated inside the material and reach finally the material surface. Surface vibration is collected by piezoelectric sensor and then amplified. Detection device of AE signal is composed with sensor coupled to the surface of material, amplifier and recorder. AE is an efficient technique for in-situ health monitoring of composite materials. This is achieved by monitoring the cumulative number of events and the analysis of AE parameters of the signal emitted by the signature waveform (hit) of internal events occurring in the material like the amplitude, the energy or the duration of the event, ... (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Schematic representation of AE wave.

The amplitude of the signal is often used because it is independent on the detection threshold. Several authors [4-6] have shown on different inorganic (glass or carbon) fiber reinforced composites that events with low amplitude (between 35–50 dB) are correlated with matrix microcracking, intermediate amplitude with delamination and microcracking coalescence (50-60dB) and matrix/fiber debonding (60-70 dB), high amplitude with fiber/matrix friction associated to pull-out (70-85 dB) and fiber breakages (>85 dB).

AE signals were monitored during monotonic tensile tests and processed with the AE acquisition and analyzing system *Mistras 2001* from Physical Acoustics Corporation (PAC). The AE signals were detected by a piezoelectric sensor (R15) attached to the sample by silicon grease and a mechanical specific device on the sample. The signals were amplified by a pre and a post-amplifier with a total gain of 70dB. The detection threshold of AE was fixed at 35dB.

2.6 Computed tomography analysis

The computed tomography is a non-destructive method based in the 3D X-ray scan which allows three-dimensional structure information of materials without contact. The micro-tomograph used is *Nanotm*[®] research edition manufactured by General Eclectic inspection Technology. It allows analysis of samples size: height from 1 mm to 120 mm, maximum 100 mm width and sample acquisition in aqueous medium. The X-ray source is an open tube GE Phoenix nano-focus, providing a maximum voltage of 180 kV and a maximum power of 15 W. The voltage range operates between 10 and 180 kV. The apparatus detector is a digital detector with dimensions 115 mm x 115 mm, with a pixel size of 50 microns x 50 microns (2300 x 2300 matrix px). It provides submicron resolution (minimum pixel size of 0.5 microns). However, the pixel resolution is highly dependent on the specimen size.

The test parameters used in this study are as follows: sample dimensions 15 mm long, 15 mm width and 4 mm thick and the beam operated at 80 keV and 120 μ A. According to the sample size the voxel resolution achieved in this study was 8 μ m. The result obtained by X-ray tomography was a stack of slices in 3 directions which includes about 2400 images. These slices were analysed using *VG-studio* and *ImageJ* to generate 3D representation of the specimens.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Materials conditioning

Effect of moisture content on PA6 based composite on mechanical properties were investigated. Specimens were dried for 8 days in a stove at 60°C, in the objective to remove all residual moisture due to air conditioning and transportation. After surface polishing of sample the absorption of water was achieved by immersion in distilled water at room temperature ($T = 23^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). Uptake moisture of specimens was measured by differential weighting using an electronic balance of accuracy 10^{-5} g. Difference between the weight of dried specimens and the weight after water immersion was calculated. Supposing that in the composite only the matrix PA6 uptakes water, the moisture content $M(t)$ absorbed by each specimen was calculated from its initial weight (w_0) of dried matrix PA6 and its weight after absorption (w_t) as follows:

$$w_0 = w_{0c} \cdot (1 - X_f) \quad (1)$$

$$w_t = w_{tc} - w_{0c} \quad (2)$$

where, (w_{0c}) is the initial weight of the composite, (X_f) is the weight fraction of the fiber (0.64) and (w_{tc}) the weight of conditioned composite at the instant t .

$$M(t) = 100 \cdot \left(\frac{w_t - w_0}{w_0} \right) \quad (3)$$

Figure 4 shows the weight gain $M(t)$ as a function of the square root of time ($t^{1/2}$) during ageing in distilled water for the studied composites. Three specimens were studied for each case and the presented water uptakes are average values.

Figure 4: Moisture content evolution as a function of time for the three composites CGFR-PA6 1 mm thick, CGFR-PA6 2 mm thick and DGFR-PA6 3 mm thick.

All composite curves showed similar shape and one can distinguish the presence of two zones. The first one is linear corresponding to a rapid increase of moisture content. The second region corresponds to a plateau at which the aged material reaches saturation. For all studied composites the kinetics of water diffusion follow the one-dimensional Fick's second law.

The coefficient of diffusion of water can be calculated from the slope (S) of the linear part of the last curves as follows [7]:

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_\infty} \right)^2 (S)^2 \quad (4)$$

where M_∞ is the moisture content at saturation, D is the apparent diffusion coefficient.

By considering the coefficients D and M_∞ , the moisture content as a function of time $M(t)$ can be expressed according to the following equation [8]:

$$\frac{M(t)}{M_\infty} = 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{8}{\pi^2(2n+1)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{D(2n+1)^2\pi^2 t}{h^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

where t is the aging time and h is the sample thickness.

The apparent diffusion coefficient and the maximum moisture content vary with the nature of composite. The continuous glass reinforced PA-6 composites achieved moisture saturation at about 8.7% with an apparent coefficient of water diffusion equal to $7.01 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ whereas the discontinuous glass reinforced PA-6 composite (DGFR-PA6) showed better hygrothermal properties since the water diffusivity and the moisture content at saturation were lower than for the CGFR-PA6 ($M_\infty = 7.7\%$ and $D = 5.1 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$).

3.2 Dynamical mechanical analysis

The storage moduli (E') and the loss factor ($\tan \delta$) as a function of the temperature and frequency for all composites were measured by DMA.

In order to accurately determine the different relaxation temperatures, CPGR-PA6 composite were oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ according to the direction of loading. Figure 5 shows an example of the evolution of storage modulus (E') and damping factor ($\tan(\delta)$) as a function of temperature and frequency for CPGR-PA6. These figures compare two moisture content states: dried and wet at saturation.

Figure5: Evolution of viscoelastic properties of CGFR-PA6 oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ measured by DMA as versus temperature and frequency : a) Storage modulus E' b) damping factor ($\tan(\delta)$).

(---) dry composite (—) wet composite.

In the range of temperature studied (-130; 200 °C) a decrease of storage modulus is observed with temperature increase. The structural change occurring in polymeric materials is a result of the molecular mobility at different time scales. These motions are known as molecular relaxations. In the case of dried composites three clear relaxations can be distinguished:

- the main relaxation or relaxation- α corresponding to the drastically decrease of the storage modulus and the highest peak of the $\tan(\delta)$; this relaxation is associated to the glass transition, and corresponds to the coordinated motion of relatively long chain segments by debonding of low energy bonds (hydrogen bonds) [9]. This relaxation occurs approximately at $T_\alpha = 80 - 90^\circ\text{C}$ depending on frequency.
- two sub- T_g relaxations [10, 11]: the relaxation- β and relaxation- γ corresponding to the motions of small chain segments or molecular functions. The relaxation- β involves the rotation of the amide functions and occurs in the range of $-80 / -40^\circ\text{C}$ approximately; the relaxation- γ corresponds to the vibrational motions of the methylene functions in the chains and it occurs at around -130°C .

After conditioning by water immersion, the DMA results show that the presence of water in the PA6 matrix involves a shift of mechanical molecular relaxations to low temperature as observed in Fig.6. In fact, the T_α decreases from 80°C in the dry composite to -10°C for the wet composite at 1Hz as shown in Fig.6 .

Figure 6: Temperature of main relaxation versus moisture content for different loading frequencies.

In the case of the main relaxation (α) the shift of temperature is due to the fact that the presence of water increases the local volume by separating the polymer chains [12, 13].

3.3 Three-point bending tests

Flexural mechanical properties of all composites according to the process conditions and moisture content were studied using 3-point bending test. The apparent flexural elastic modulus (E_f) and the ultimate stress (σ_{max}) were the mechanical properties evaluated. The linear part of curve corresponds to the elastic behavior and the maximum recorded stress is considered as the ultimate flexural stress.

Analysis of unaged composites

Figure 7 compares the flexural properties of the monolithic composites: Continuous GFR-PA6 and Discontinuous GFR-PA6 for the different processing conditions and sampling zones. In all the cases a macroscopic failure occurred on the tensile side.

The results show there is no significant variation in the apparent flexural modulus for the two composites whatever the processing conditions. Nevertheless, there is a large modulus range for discontinuous fiber reinforced composite (7-16 GPa) due to the fiber architecture which varies with sampling zone.

Figure 7: Evolution of apparent flexural modulus according to the temperature process variation: a) CGFR-PA6 and b) DGFR-PA6 (for two different sampling zones (blue & red)).

Due to the multi-layering feature of these composites, two bending configurations were investigated for the over-molded: in the first, continuous glass fibers on the tensile side and in the second on the compressive side. Fig. 8.a and Fig. 8.b show the homogenized apparent flexural modulus and the ultimate flexural strength respectively of over-molded composites. These figures compare the flexural properties for different processing temperatures.

Figure 8: Flexural properties for the over-molded composite: a) apparent flexural modulus b) ultimate flexural strength c) and d) illustration of different bending configurations and failure features.

The results show that there is no clear tendency concerning the apparent flexural modulus according to the temperature processing and bending configuration. This behavior is probably associated to the complex fiber architecture according to sampling zone (Fig.8.a). The ultimate flexural strength evolution according to the different configurations is shown in figure (Fig. 8.b). When the CGFR-PA6 is on the tensile side the flexural strength is the highest and quasi-stable whatever the processing conditions. For the configuration with the discontinuous fibers on the tensile side the ultimate stress increases with the processing conditions probably due to a better interface between the two composites. This assumption was confirmed using computed tomography technique which allows investigating failure mode of the over-molded systems. Fig.9 shows an example of 3D reconstitution computed from X-ray slices for continuous glass fibers on the tensile side (Fig. 9.a) and discontinuous glass fibers on the tensile side (Fig. 9.b). These figures show typical failure features. In the case when CGFR-PA6 is on the tensile side the failure grows through the two composites (Fig. 9.a). In the second case (discontinuous fibers on the tensile mode) the failure occurs through the discontinuous glass fiber composite and at the interface between the two materials (Fig. 9.b).

Figure 9: 3D micro-tomography representation of over-molded composite after 3-point bending test: a) CGFR-A6 on the tensile side and b) DGFR-A6 on the tensile side.

Moreover, this analysis confirms that the scattering of the results is due to the fiber architecture of the injected composite. In fact, the injection flow makes the fiber orientation: in some cases the skin/core morphology is dominant with high thickness of skin layer and with fibers oriented principally in longitudinal direction, leading to a higher strength. Figure 10 shows two over-molded composites with the same process parameters but with different ultimate flexural strengths (a: $\sigma_{max} = 190$ MPa, b: $\sigma_{max} = 312$ MPa).

Figure 10: Micro-tomography slices showing discontinuous fibers orientation for the same process conditions but different sampling zones.

Effect of moisture on flexural properties

Figure 11 illustrates the evolution of apparent flexural modulus (Fig.11.a) and ultimate flexural strength (Fig.11.b) as a function of moisture content for all studied composites for a given sampling zone.

The results show a sharp decrease in the flexural modulus as well as in the ultimate flexural strength. The continuous glass fibres reinforced PA6 observes a decrease of 50% in both apparent flexural modulus and ultimate flexural strength for the moisture saturation state. At 5% of moisture content the decrease of flexural modulus is about 50% and the flexural strength was reduced of about 36%.

Figure 11: Evolution of flexural properties according to the moisture content for all composites: a) apparent flexural modulus and b) ultimate flexural stress.

As shown previously with DMA, the absorbed water decreases the main relaxation of PA6 due to the plasticizing action of water molecules. This phenomenon leads to a drop of the modulus of the matrix at room temperature, and therefore to a decrease of the composite one (mixture law). Moreover, the increase in molecular mobility of the wet matrix reduces the yield stress and increases the ductility and elongation at break of the composite.

For the composites CGFR-PA6, no macroscopic failure was observed on the tensile side whereas some visible micro-damage occurred in the central zone of the compressive side. Acoustic emission activity allowed distinguishing different damage mechanisms for these composites at dry and wet states (Fig.12). The dry specimen (Fig.12.a) exhibited amplitude histogram with two peaks. The low amplitude AE (below 60 dB) was due to matrix microcracking and fibre/matrix micro-debonding, whereas the middle range amplitude hits accounted for the second peak (between 60 and 85 dB) were associated to pull-out phenomenon. Some AE events of high amplitude (85-100 dB) are also revealed suggesting breakage of fibers, the interface fiber/matrix being strong enough to transfer stresses from matrix to fiber. For wet composites AE amplitudes are mainly distributed between 35 dB and 60 dB (Fig.12.b). This may confirm matrix and fiber/matrix interface weakening by the water absorption finally causing fiber micro-buckling which is governed by the matrix shear modulus occurring on the compressive side and plastic deformation without any pull-out on the tensile side.

Figure 12: AE hits versus amplitude during 3-point bending test: a) dry composite and b) wet composite $M(t) = 4\%$, processing pre-heating temperature 275°C .

3.4 Tensile test

In the aim to evaluate the effect of process manufacturing condition on mechanical properties only the continuous glass fiber reinforced PA6 composites were tested in tensile loading. Digital stereo correlation was used to calculate field strain and acoustic emission was used to determine different events which occur during test. Figure (Fig.13) shows an example of strain evolution with stress increase. The strains were calculated according the two major directions E1: following the loading direction and E2 perpendicular to the loading direction. The results illustrate that the dried CGFR-PA6 composites show a linear behavior to failure. However, the water conditioned specimens undergo a non-linear behavior at high strain associated to yielding.

Figure 13: Example of stress vs strain curves for two process temperature condition in: a) dry state and b) wet state $M(t) = 8\%$.

From the stress-strain curves Young's moduli and ultimate tensile strength were determined. The Young's modulus was calculated from the slope between the calculated strain and the stress in the linear region. The ultimate tensile strength was taken as the maximal stress before failure. Figure (Fig.13) shows the evolution of Young's modulus (a) and ultimate tensile strength (b) as a function of temperature process conditions and moisture content in the composite.

Figure 14: Evolution of tensile properties according to pre-heating temperature: a) Young's modulus and b) ultimate tensile strength.

Increased preheat temperatures improved tensile mechanical properties of dry composites while remaining below 295° at which a stabilization or a slight decrease is observed. Preheat temperatures directly affect the matrix viscosity. The lowering of the viscosity allows fiber impregnation during forming, and therefore fiber/matrix interface improvement leading to a higher laminate quality. Nevertheless a possible drawback may be disturbances in fiber orientation as the preheat temperature increases.

For the very severely aged composites the tensile properties, especially the ultimate strength, were lowered whatever processing temperature (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**). The amplitude of this phenomenon is less pronounced for the highest pre-heating conditions (295°), probably due to a decrease in void content. Indeed voids could amplify the effect of moisture adsorption [14].

Figure 15: AE hits versus amplitude during tensile test: a) unaged composite and b) aged composite M(t) = 5%, processing pre-heating temperature 275°C.

Conversely bending analysis, the amplitude histogram exhibited similar features for dry and wet specimen (8 %) (Fig. 15): the amplitude shows a quasi-triangular-shaped appearance over a range between 40 dB and about 80 dB indicating different damage mechanisms as matrix cracking, fiber/matrix debonding, delamination and pull-out. Some AE events of high amplitude (80-100 dB) are also shown suggesting fiber failures. However, the number of events greatly decreases with ageing: this may suggest fiber/matrix interface weakening and matrix plasticization due to water absorption. These results are consistent with ultimate strength trend with moisture increase.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study the thermomechanical and mechanical properties of PA6 composites was investigated. This work demonstrates that the conditioning history and environment conditions are important parameters to be taken into account in design of structural part composites based on PA6. The PA6 matrix is very sensitive to humidity; the sorption of water can decrease drastically the thermal and mechanical properties of glass fiber reinforced PA6 composites. The over-molding of

prepreg composite can be a solution to enhance the rigidity and therefore the mechanical properties of composite parts by a local addition of discontinuous glass fiber reinforced composite.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. L. Monson, M. Braunwarth, and C.W Extrand, Moisture absorption by various polyamides and their associated dimensional changes, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, (107), 2008, pp 355-363.
- [2]. M. Schwander, Haute cadence, Haute performance, *Plastiques & caoutchoucs magazine*, Octobre 2014, N° 915, pp.54-57.
- [3]. P. Pineau, G. Huguet, Lightweight materials for engine and body works, *5th ICAC*, 2014, Cologne, Germany.
- [4]. C. Flament, M. Salvia, B. Berthel, G. Crosland, Local Strain and Damage Measurements on a Composite with Digital Image Correlation and Acoustic Emission, *EWSHM - 7th European Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring*, Jul 2014, Nantes, France, pp. 679-685.
- [5]. O. Ceysson, M. Salvia, L. Vincent, "Damage mechanisms characterisation of carbon fibre/epoxy composite laminates by both electrical resistance measurements and acoustic emission analysis", *Scripta Materialia*, (34:8), 1996, pp. 1273-1280.
- [6]. S. Barré, M.L. Benzeggagh, "On the use of acoustic emission to investigate damage mechanisms in glass-fibre-reinforced polypropylene", *Composites Science and Technology*, (52:3), 1994, pp. 369-376
- [7]. C.H. Shen, G.S. Springer, Moisture Absorption and Desorption of Composite Materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, (10) , 1976, pp. 2-20.
- [8]. W. Jost, Diffusion in Solids, Liquids, Gases. *New York: Academic Press*, 1960.
- [9]. A. Owen, R. Bonart, Cooperative relaxation processes in polymers, *Polymer*, (26), 1985, p 1034.
- [10]. Y. Park, J. Ko, T-K. Ahn, and S. Choe, Moisture Effects on the Glass Transition and the Low Temperature Relaxations in Semiaromatic Polyamides, *J. Polym. Sci. Part B: Polym. Phys.*, (35), 1997, p. 807.
- [11]. G. Rotter and H. Ishida, Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of the Glass Transition: Curve Resolving Applied to Polymers, *Macromolecules*, (25), 1992, p.2170.
- [12]. N. S. Murthy, M. K. Akkapedi, Analysis of lamellar structure in semicrystalline polymers by studying the absorption of water and ethylene glycol in nylons small angle neutron scattering, *Macromolecules*, (3), 1998, pp. 142-152.
- [13]. Bergeret, L. Ferry, P. Ienny. Vieillesse hygrothermique des composites thermoplastiques renforcés par des fibres de verre, *Revue des composites et des matériaux avancés*, (18)1, 2008, pp. 33-49.
- [14]. Y. Zhang, D. H. Li, D. X. Zhang, H. B. Lu, H. Y. Xiao, J. Jia, Qualitative separation of the effect of voids on the static mechanical properties of hygrothermally conditioned carbon/epoxy composites, *eXPRESS Polymer Letters*, (5:8), 2011, pp. 708-716.